

The African Man in Ethnographic Cinema: A Study of Documentary Achievements

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ABSTRACT: *The African man has largely maintained his form and traditions despite urbanization, striving to preserve his cultural heritage and mythical beliefs that have characterized his way of life. Most of his traditions and living conditions are characterized by simplicity, as he has been and continues to be content with minimal sustenance and wears only goatskin or half a jacket in some tribes that maintain the authenticity of their cultural heritage. Moreover, he does not favor a life of isolation but lives in social harmony without expectation of return. This study focuses on describing the way of life of the African man and what the artistic achievements documented through ethnographic cinema reveal to us.*

KEYWORDS: African man, ethnographic cinema, art correspondence, belief.

RÉSUMÉ : *L'homme africain a largement conservé sa forme et ses traditions malgré l'urbanisation, s'efforçant de préserver son patrimoine culturel et ses croyances mythiques qui ont caractérisé son mode de vie. La plupart de ses traditions et de ses conditions de vie se distinguent par leur simplicité, car il a été et continue d'être satisfait avec un minimum de subsistance, ne portant que des peaux de chèvre ou une demi-veste dans certaines tribus qui préservent l'authenticité de leur patrimoine culturel. De plus, il ne privilégie pas une vie d'isolement mais vit en harmonie sociale sans attendre de retour. Cette étude se concentre sur la description du mode de vie de l'homme africain et ce que les réalisations artistiques documentées à travers le cinéma ethnographique nous révèlent.*

MOTS-CLÉS: Homme africain, cinéma ethnographique, correspondance artistique, croyance.

Introduction

The arts in Africa play a significant role in the social and cultural diversity of the human environment, drawn from a wide array of cultural knowledge spanning forty centuries. These arts have shaped functions that have led to many works in the fields of ancestor and deity worship, among other supernatural forces. They serve as symbols of power and are used by members of the social, political, and religious elite. Key themes include the creations of artists from the court of Benin in Nigeria, major sculptures from West and Central Africa, devotional works of the Ethiopian Orthodox Church, and ancient gold and ceramic artifacts associated with the regions of Colombia and Mexico, as well as works of North America's indigenous peoples.

The fundamental role of the African man is to maintain the existence and continuity of African peoples by establishing identity and preserving customs, traditions, and spiritual and religious values, as well as social integration. Ethnographic cinema in these societies serves as an expression that describes beliefs, values, emotions, and entertainment, or it represents the psychological atmosphere. The concept of ethnography appears to reflect the human desire to depict and embody things that are rarely felt or that dominate one's life without being noticed. While the African man does not see or hear spirits and gods, through masks and rituals, he attempts to act as the gods do. Thus, representation provides the African man with a form of psychological satisfaction in expressing things he wishes for but that cannot happen.

Thus, the researcher poses the main problem as follows:

How did the African man express the journey of the self through ethnographic documentaries? And what is the nature of this expression in the documentary film 'Africa on Foot: Hamar Tribes'?

The importance of this research lies in its being a modern scientific study that keeps pace with new developments in the world of artistic ethnography. It unveils the deep interiors of the documentary film, which allows insight into the culture of African society. Moreover, it possesses ideas aimed at depicting what should be portrayed in a world where the African man sought to explore his anthropology and cultural identity.

1. The journey of arts and their correspondence in Africa

Africa, the cradle of humanity and the oldest region inhabited by humans, is extremely ethnographically diverse. It boasts a rich artistic and cultural history with various civilizations, containing a thousand ethnic groups speaking a thousand languages. This diversity has contributed to the establishment and reinforcement of a unique artistic character in Africa, evident in rituals, magical practices, craft heritage, traditions, spiritual beliefs related to nature, life, death, fear, worship, traditional religions, hunting methods, rainmaking, moments of triumph and predation, enemy combat, judiciary practices, and the wrestling of beasts, as well as the reverence of ancestors by primitive Africans. Among the cultural manifestations that have spread in African societies, varied between a set of intertwined spiritual and material values, is the use of these arts in providing various means of livelihood, such as pots, plates, spoons, drinking vessels, seats, beds, necklaces, human decoration and beautification elements, weapons for defense, hunting tools, and other necessities for humans in a rural environment where life is based on agriculture, animal products, and hunting.

1.1 Architecture and sculpture in Africa

The ancient remains in Africa reveal that houses were built from wood and some ceramic or clay materials, with pottery being a fundamental material in house construction (Shaaban & Ali, 2004, p. 23). These houses are characterized by their simplicity, although they differ from one region to another in terms of their external shape and appearance. Sometimes the houses are rectangular, sometimes square, but they are usually built in a circular form, as seen in Sudan and Mali. African villages are typically surrounded by walls to protect them from external invasions, often featuring forts and castles around them, as in Nigeria. The houses of the poor differ from those of the rich, which are adorned with decorations and wall paintings, as evidenced by the palaces of dignitaries in Cameroon. Religious buildings, temples, and mosques are characterized by their simplicity.

The houses built by the African man and the way he organized his residential communities reflect the constraints imposed by the environment and its necessities, mirroring the living patterns and the African man's perception of the individual, family, and social life. Architectural design also reflects the general expectation of the nature of

the environment and how the African man uses resources. "African architects left very little in the way of significant buildings, but what they did leave behind was ingeniously adapted to their environment and resources."

Modern Architecture Despite the emergence of a few schools (Kinshasa, Luanda, Maputo) that have produced some upcoming architects, traditional architects remain predominantly in North Africa. Elsewhere, houses are becoming increasingly standardized in design, often built by their users themselves (Mazrui, 1999, p. 633). Architectural design can reflect beliefs or political ideas in a general and somewhat enduring form. While houses and local communities in technologically less developed societies have a shorter lifespan compared to their counterparts in modern cities, we can still observe the interaction between physical elements, environmental factors, and the ideal models humans have formed about family and social life. In traditional societies, architectural design may not clearly express independence and distinctiveness.

The most influential figure in West African architecture was the Cordoban architect Abu Ishaq Ibrahim al-Sahili, who arrived in Mali with Sultan Musa in 1325 CE and introduced modern building techniques. He successfully constructed several brick and stone mosques in Timbuktu and Gao (Al-Ghoneimi, 1986). The shape and design of a building or house become clear upon the completion of construction. Even structures built in an impromptu manner reflect culturally regulated patterns for the distribution of their inhabitants and users, as well as the activities they engage in. These structures often possess a symbolic character that expresses the relationship between the house and a particular person, group, or other entities.

African sculpture, which has flourished over long periods, has always been connected to the spirit of myths, the magic of the Negroes, and has carried customs, traditions, and religious rituals in stunning artistic forms rarely found in other countries, especially in terms of aesthetic value. This art form still garners significant interest in the continent, particularly in Senegal, as it has penetrated the economic world, providing a source of livelihood. Despite this, "the stone building system was introduced, along with the use of sand and wood. Skilled craftsmen in carving, decoration, and architecture emerged. In Zanzibar, we find beautiful

buildings constructed in Arab and Indian styles. Artists excelled in beautifying and decorating these buildings, adorning mosques, palaces, and exquisite artifacts, as well as decorating doors and windows with beautiful drawings (Al-Khuwailidi, p. 157)." However, the African man has maintained his connection to paganism, with most sculptors believing that their stone, clay, and wooden sculptures have a spiritual function and the ability to bring safety by warding off spirits. This art includes masks, sculptures, and decorative forms used in celebrations and social events. Unfortunately, African sculpture was primarily based on wood, making it vulnerable to decay. "As in all of Africa, sculptors among the Fang people are not considered mere anonymous executors. John Lode, relying on the views of William Fagg and Michel Leiris among others, demonstrated that the field of African sculpture, contrary to common belief, is not devoid of creators. Among the Fang people, as in other regions, the sculptor is known to the people, sought after at times, and is regarded as a talented artist (Vinith & Crowley, 2014, p. 62)."

In Tin Hinan, we find small clay statues representing shapes of birds, women, and cows, with one cow statue still having two small branches serving as horns. There are two notable features of this art: the first lies in the use of strong colors, which can be seen on masks made for magical purposes and religious rituals, where skins are used and animals are painted on them. The second feature is the use of shells and bird feathers to decorate the sculptures, adding an aesthetic touch to them.

Figure 1. represents a form of architecture used in African civilization known as Tata.

Thus, the dwelling occupies a fundamental position in African societies, being one of the key factors ensuring the continuation of social life. It primarily serves as a shelter, providing places to sleep, protection from weather changes, and safety from wild animals. The main function of the dwelling was not for eating, as meals were typically taken outside, nor was it for physical rest, which also occurred outside the home. Instead, the dwelling was a civilized tool through which humans overcame various conditions such as cold, rain, and sunlight. Consequently, different forms of dwellings spread across all civilizations, offering protection from both the climate and sudden threats, enemies, and predators.

The form of the dwelling evolved from using caves as shelters for human groups to structures built with various materials depending on the type of civilization and the prevalent resources. These dwellings met humans' biological needs for comfort, relaxation, and eating, as well as social inheritance. People spend a long time in their parents' homes and become accustomed to a certain layout of the dwelling and furniture, making changes difficult. Therefore, the evolution in the type and layout of dwellings is very slow. There are bedrooms and meeting rooms, with the addition of the kitchen and bathroom as separate rooms. In the Stone Age and among some primitive groups, the kitchen was a communal hearth. During the Middle Ages and in ancient cities, the kitchen was part of the living room, serving as a hearth for warmth and cooking. This is still the case in rural areas around the world.

1.2. In African dances and chants

Dance is always linked to music and can be considered a form of art, entertainment, or religious activity. Each of these activities can have its own dances or can merge into a single dance. The nature and formation of the dance are dictated by the occasion or the type of celebration. Dances vary based on their uses, symbolism, customs, and the instruments employed, and they are influenced by the nature of the economic activity. For instance, communities that rely on hunting often have dances that mimic the chase between the hunter and the prey.

Looking at the impact of music and its various uses, one will be amazed to discover that it is a universal cultural feature. Some of these uses include protest, communication, dance, expression of love, insult, work, healing, hunting, divination and magic, storytelling, mourning, political support, and education.

Dance is one of the most prominent arts among Africans. They dance and sway in groups or individually, regardless of the distances between them or the differences in their beliefs and religions. G. Gore, in his 1930 book titled "Africa Dances," says: "They dance in joy as they dance in sorrow, they dance in love as they dance in hate, they dance to bring wealth as they dance to ward off misfortune, they dance as a religious ritual as they dance to fill their leisure time (Mazrui, 1999, p. 667)." For Africans, dance is an almost instinctive inclination, evident in tribes practicing dance and wearing special headgear. They dance whether they have musical accompaniment or whether the dance itself is accompanied by certain types of cries or group singing.

African dance is often accompanied by the rhythm of drumbeats and trumpet sounds, with dancers competing in their movements. Each dance is distinguished by specific shouts and accompanying sounds, along with various decorations such as fur pieces, hunting skins, bird feathers, and metal rings that produce a ringing sound throughout the dance. "At the same time, rural dance styles have endured and continued to grow. The dynamism of this art is evident as even after 1900, a new composite style of traditional theatrical ballet dance called bobongo developed in parts of Zaire despite the colonial situation (Mazrui, 1999, p. 667)." There are dances involving both men and women, such as the welcome dance, the love dance, the dance to approach the gods, the hunting dance, the war dance, and even the death dance. Music is closely related to these dances, with African drums being some of the most widespread musical instruments. Many of these drums are made from large bamboo, while others are crafted from hollowed-out tree trunks and covered with thin animal skins.

The rituals involving masks are usually agricultural or funerary and are often accompanied by hymns, music, and storytelling, creating a harmonious blend of colors, movement, dance, and singing. "Most masks are carved from wood, although some are made from cloth and other

materials. They are often decorated with paint, beads, cloth, or animal fibers, tightly fastened to produce varying sounds."

Figure 2. illustrates the features of African dance with drums and artistic chants, creating a musical rhythm with traditional musical instruments. The functions of music also appear in the political realm through songs that praise leaders. Even the instruments used have meanings and functions, such as drums symbolizing political power among many African peoples. It is often prohibited for anyone outside the leader's or king's family to possess such drums. The roles of music in social systems are evident in birth, marriage, and death ceremonies. One of the most notable functions in social regulation includes songs accompanied by music and dance, which denounce those who neglect their duties or condemn incidents of social injustice, among other social control factors. Hence, African music has functional value in two main ways:

- It is fully integrated with other forms of daily life activities.
- It is practiced and enjoyed by a large number of people in the community. Music is an activity in which the audience participates alongside the performers, and almost everyone is proficient in singing and practices it.

1.3 The ritual mask in the realm of religion

The history of African masks combines religious and spiritual meanings, traditionally used in ritual dances and celebratory activities. The mask itself lacks any form of realistic human features, leading to various abstract interpretations. It was believed that African masks resembling

animals embodied the spirit of the mentioned animal. Buffaloes, crocodiles, and antelopes were among the most common themes, especially in Dogon and Bambara cultures, where masks were used by dancers in rites of passage ceremonies.

Masks can be divided into two main categories: face masks, which cover only the face, and helmet masks, which cover the entire head. Among the Baule, a branch of the Akan people in West Africa, there are multiple types of masks, each with a known function. Baule masks are worn to protect the community from dangers, during harvest festivals, to honor distinguished guests, to entertain, or to commemorate the dead (Kanda, 2016, p. 22). Wearing masks is exclusively a male activity, and women are not allowed to see them. However, in some communities such as those in India and Sierra Leone, there are specific rituals for women during funerals or at the beginning of planting or harvest seasons.

Figure 3. illustrates a funerary dance with masks among the Dogon people in Mali

Thus, wearing masks is akin to invoking the significant forces that created the world and societies. The function of the mask is to emphasize the reality of myths in daily life, and they are used differently at the beginning of rituals. "The masks inspired by the Africans in their creation are examples of their rich imagination, such as the Bobo masks, particularly the three main ones: Kile (the ancient mask), Kimi (with the head of the grey crowned crane), and Tibile (which has a skull). These masks represent real characters known in the village, serving as historical

witnesses and actively contributing to its creation (KI-Zerbo, 1990, p. 364)."

Young men are gathered outside the village and subjected to a series of trials to measure their physical and moral maturity. They undergo educational stages that reveal some secret religious details and instill respect for the community's laws in their minds. The mask occasionally appears as an embodiment of the spirit that created humanity. It is also used for protection against invaders and witches, serves as a political pressure tool in the hands of monks, and is used in dances preceding battles. The mask is designed to absorb the life force that escapes from a person or animal at the moment of death." For example, among the Senufo people in Ivory Coast, a particular type of mask facilitates the deceased's spirit's transition to the afterlife, ensuring its departure from this world. Pregnant women are forbidden from watching this dance, fearing the sight might harm the fetuses. The Senufo also believe that the life-giving power of women could prevent the deceased's spirit from moving to the other world (Kanda, 2016, p. 23)." The living force released at the moment of death roams and causes distress to the living, visible in the disturbance on their faces.

Masks can capture and harness these forces, which can then be distributed for the common good. Masks also protect the dancer during rituals from the tools they handle. Unlike statues, masks encompass both animal and human features. Face painting is also considered a type of mask and is removed after the rituals are performed. Since face painting is temporary and only lasts for the duration of the dance, it should be distinguished from tattoos, skin scars, or dental modifications, which leave a permanent mark and are derived from social customs rather than ritual masks.

1.4 The clothing and local folklore in African culture

The African individual takes great care of their appearance and natural features using artificial means, attempting to assert their identity appropriately. They beautify or conceal or alter their personal appearance, such as their features, skin, and hair. They adorn themselves with personal decorations and cover themselves with clothes for protection or to distinguish themselves from others. Personal hygiene varies according to tribal characteristics and is often not related to the abundance or

scarcity of water. Many communities prioritize regular washing before and after meals, before and after official duties like visits, or during ritual ceremonies. Some communities apply oil, fat, or fine ash to their bodies, perhaps to keep the skin in a natural state to protect against insects or external parasites. There are designated places and tools for washing and bathing, which differ among various communities. These may include specific scents for the body and clothes, and perfumes to mask natural odors or to enhance sexual attraction.

Thus, African attire underwent a radical transformation "from nudity to an elegance that commands respect from others... The Muslims there were particularly keen to appear in loose-fitting garments, wearing the finest clothes. This trend began with the royal family, courtiers, high-ranking officials, the elite, the wealthy, traders, and scholars, eventually spreading to the general African populace who adopted these garments as their attire (Al-Ghoneimi, 1986, p. 98)." As a result, clothing in these regions became characterized by adornment with gold bracelets, gold chains, and other items with which African women decorated themselves. Leather clothing was common among the general population, especially in winter and in hot desert areas. Hairstyles were used for adornment and to distinguish between individuals, genders, and social ranks, such as leaders, married and unmarried people. These styles varied from one community to another, with some people keeping their hair short while others left it uncut.

Figure 4. illustrates the role of the razor blade in shaping the concept of adornment among African men, with some tribes intentionally agitating wounds to make scars more pronounced.

Regarding nails, African people took care of their nails by regularly trimming their fingernails. Some even pierced and painted their nails, using various colors and materials for the polish.

Folklore holds a prestigious position among African peoples and is considered as essential as oxygen. It has been employed in various aspects of daily life for a long time, such as in education, medicine, law, and traditional techniques. Traditional education and social reform primarily take the form of folktales, riddles, proverbs, historical legends, traditional festivals, crafts, and material culture, all of which are considered folklore. "Some definitions are usually given to traditional artistic and literary creations. In some countries, folklore definitions take a broader meaning to include other aspects, such as scientific or technological folklore, encompassing theoretical and scientific information in natural sciences, physics, mathematics, astronomy, and artistic knowledge for the production and manufacturing of medicines, textiles, metalwork, and other products (Hadid, p. 19)." African folklore provides the basis for vocational education for the common man and specialized training for traditional experts, whether healers, astrologers, traditional religious figures, poets, or blacksmiths. It is an education for life through life.

Traditional medicine is considered common knowledge available to any individual, and when specialized expertise is needed, it is accessible within the village or neighboring villages. These specialists are widespread throughout Africa with various names, functions, and healing abilities. Among them are herbalists, seers, bone setters, cuppers, saints like healers and scholars, and leaders of spiritual practices. Traditional medicine has remained the most prevalent due to the limited availability of modern medical services and the African communities' trust in the healing abilities of traditional practitioners.

2. How is an ethnographic film constructed in the context of interweaving artistic knowledge?

An ethnographic film is a cinematic genre that relies on documenting, recording, and presenting reality without interference or fabrication. This

distinguishes it from fictional films, where the filmmaker has full authority to shape both real and fictional events according to their vision. Ethnographic films integrate reality with reality, especially in documentary dramas and films that address issues trying to influence reality. These films allow the weaving together of various events and require not distorting or exaggerating reality. The most common definition of a documentary film is the creative treatment of reality.

Therefore, "an ethnographic film is a documentary genre with its uniqueness derived from its use of documentation based on reality. It is a non-fiction film concerned with real aspects such as people, places, and actual events rather than imaginary ones. It relies on mobility, observation, and selection from life itself. It does not depend on an author's themes or actors in an artificial environment, nor does it rely on professional actors. Its scenes are filmed with both artificial and natural lighting from the real, living reality, capturing the authenticity to genuinely portray its subject matter (researchers, 2011, p. 126)."

The characteristics and behavioral patterns of these societies are rich in meanings, symbols, and connotations. Between the poetic nature of the place, its authenticity, its pristine state, and perhaps its harshness, and the time difference that separates these societies from the real timeline of humanity, the role of imagery and the filmed document becomes crucial in conveying reality and depicting truth. This is a method of creating meaning through the fabric of the film. Consequently, documentary films are divided into two levels.

The higher level involves the filmmaker being capable of recording and creating, adhering to the rules of documentary filmmaking and reference films. The lower level includes reports, educational films, and reportage, where the director may liberate many of the documentary film rules, such as film duration, sound and editing techniques, language, and active elements.

The issue of defining the term for this type of film, which was popularized among filmmakers by John Grierson, who depicted reality creatively, highlights the difficulty in reaching a logical definition for the ethnographic documentary film. This type relies on capturing direct real-life events, making it a subject or a story. The term's origins trace back to

1923 when the concept of the documentary was first used to describe any film that uses documents taken from reality.

The artistic structural levels of an ethnographic documentary film include (Arheim, 2020):

- Employing ethnography in film production.
- Truth in ethnographic documentary films.
- Writing the ethnographic documentary film.
- Consulting in the ethnographic documentary film.
- Descriptive study of the ethnographic documentary film.
- Narration in the ethnographic documentary film.
- Events in the ethnographic documentary film.
- Characters in the ethnographic documentary film.
- Expressive sound in the ethnographic documentary film.
- Cultural change in the ethnographic documentary film.

A documentary film is considered an individual effort compared to a fictional film. There is a significant difference in filming between documentary and fictional films, which directly impacts the editing process. The editing of fictional films tends to lean towards representational presentation. We can say that a documentary film does not contain a visual or mental equivalent for everything it presents. Documentary films involve less manipulation and cannot resemble full-length fictional films. Often, the filmmaker cannot control the event they are developing. There is less control and manipulation regarding the subjects of documentary films (Al-Hassan, 2015).

Thus, we summarize that an ethnographic film, theoretically, is a cinematic genre that relies on documenting and recording reality through two levels. The first, higher level, involves creating the film with the ability to analyze and create. The second, lower level, includes reports, educational films, and reportage. Fictional films today incorporate a degree of documentary craftsmanship and vice versa. Fictional films have followed theatrical traditions in their subjects precisely and, over time, have replaced theatrical forms with cinematic forms and theatrical acting with cinematic acting.

An ethnographic film is a term with many connotations, often defined as a film about other cultures, Western peoples, or customs and traditions. Based on this principle, television program makers agree on documentary

films that provide entertainment and amusement, whether in a charming or shocking style, through content about Western peoples. Independent filmmakers, such as Les Blank, who explored Western musical and culinary cultures worldwide with empathy and respect, are pleased with this approach.

3. The ethnographic achievement in the film "Africa on foot hamar tribes" as a model

Idea and Preparation	Loay Al-Attibi
Director of Photography	Wasim Nahra
Scriptwriting for Voiceover	Nabil Osman
Editing and Mixing	Saed Arouri
Production	Al Jazeera Documentary
Year of Production	2014
Duration	55:34 m

Table 1.

3.1 A study on the origins of Ethiopian society

Ethiopians held a significant place in Roman thought, similar to their status in Greek thought previously. This was due to the political and military confrontations, as well as economic and social connections and interests between them and the Romans. This is a common situation in the intermingling of ancient civilizations. Ethiopia is mentioned and appears in the Odyssey as a favored place for the Greek sea god. In several instances in the fifth book of this epic, Homer, through the voice of 'Poseidon,' refers to his return from the homeland of his Ethiopian friends (Al-Nuaimi, 2013, p. 13). They live in the far south of Ethiopia near the Omo River, southwest Kenya, and to the east is Sudan, with a population of around 42,000. They live in a simple environment that heavily depends on nature, whether in building their homes, using cooking utensils, preserving food, or even producing alcohol for all uses, which is extracted from trees. All sources of their livelihood are derived from nature, similar to how primitive humans lived. Through this research, we explore the impact of the interaction between biological, social, and cultural aspects on the demographic characteristics of human

societies, clarifying the effects of urbanization, modernization, migration, and ethnic conflicts on the population structure.

Ethnic minorities in Ethiopia have historically played and continue to play a role in shaping the structure of Ethiopian society, contributing to its religious, linguistic, social, and artistic heritage diversity. The United Nations classifies these groups as cultural minorities. According to the political dictionary, minorities are defined as "citizens of states who, in terms of race, language, religion, or other aspects, belong to a group different from the majority of their fellow citizens." Similarly, sociologists and anthropologists define a minority as "a group that differs in its ethnic, religious, and linguistic composition from the rest of the population in the society in which it lives (Hanoush, 1997)."

This definition helps explain the behaviors of certain tribes, such as the 'Hamer' tribe, which might be seen as negative or peculiar from our perspective, or as contrary to civilized human norms (Misbah, 2019, p. 15). An example is the practice known as 'Mingi,' a ritual leading to the killing of infants and children, not only among the 'Hamer' tribe but also among African tribes in the lower part of the Omo Valley in southwestern Ethiopia. Infants are subjected to this fate if they develop upper teeth before lower ones, are born out of wedlock, or are born without their parents having received marriage approval. Tribal elders order the killing of all Mingi children by filling their mouths with dirt, leaving them alone in the wilderness without food or water, or drowning them in the river. These children are considered omens of bad luck, bringing evil spirits, curses, and drought to the village.

The gods they worship or pray to do not exist in a specific form. Rather, their worship involves rituals performed by the tribe leader to invoke rain. He drinks water soaked with coffee or other substances, then blows from his mouth onto the homes of his people as a blessing, praying and hoping for rain, which is considered vital. Water, as a sacred element in all practices, represents the source of life and a transition from death to life. All historical and archaeological discoveries confirm that humans do not settle in places without water. Therefore, the Hamer tribe attempted to settle in lowland areas to avoid the danger that rain poses to them and their livestock. Consequently, the rainwater would gather and flow to

these lowland areas, acting as a reservoir that the earth retains for extraction when needed and to preserve it from drought.

However, this settlement imposed a significant burden on the women, who are tasked with fetching water, among other strenuous duties. Even their method of hair decoration, which is specific to married women, is peculiar and challenging. Every two weeks, Hamer women color and style their hair uniquely. They use a mixture of clay, cow butter, and gasoline, combined with sand, and twist each strand of hair individually.

3.2 The social aspect of Ethiopian men's lives

It is acknowledged that practices and rituals are deeply rooted in our daily lives. What is known in anthropology as customs and rituals is essentially a series of ceremonies and occasions in some religions, and hymns and traditions in others and different regions, carried out in a celebratory space. The term "celebration" encompasses two elements: human and life (Karim, 1985, p. 187). Thus, a celebration is an expression of life, considered a purely human festivity. This is evident in all aspects of their lives, including eating, marriage, engagement ceremonies, and the presentation of dowries, among other life events they experience.

There is no doubt that culture held a high status in this civilization. The Hamer tribe, for instance, had several alphabets used by the educated and the tribal leaders for managing the tribe's affairs. The commemorative plaques and the archaeological findings passed down from generation to generation bear inscriptions in a single language. Most anthropologists use the term "acculturation" to signify socialization, maintaining distinct cultural patterns and disseminating them across generations. This perspective on political socialization or acculturation views the acquisition and absorption of culture as an almost automatic process (Misbah, 2019, p. 151). Through this process, individuals in the Hamer tribe acquire culture simply by being exposed to it over time.

Figure

However, Ethiopian culture is based on principles derived from the Bible and Christianity. Since Christianity established itself in Ethiopia, the Bible became the source of all human knowledge. The individual worthy of being called Ethiopian was not one who studied the origins of culture and society through philosophy but rather one who was knowledgeable about the Bible, Saint John Chrysostom, and other founders of the church. This provides religious and social perceptions shaped by a system of beliefs and spiritual concepts, where the spirits of ancestors and natural phenomena represented the components of these practices in the Hamar tribe.

Accordingly, it should be noted that traditional African thought practiced in the Hamar tribe views all these cosmic elements in human life as the foundation of religious, social, and cultural principles. This traditional thought serves as the core of the universe, accompanied by beliefs that influence the anthropological environment and the relationship between the artist and life and existence. This creates an idea based on reality and imagination without a dividing objective or aesthetic barrier. Thus, the local folklore heritage is divided according to the anthropological practice of the individual and society:

- **Social Cultural Heritage:** This pertains to all practices, behaviors, and beliefs established by ancestors, whose foundation is linked to social customs, traditions, and the oral heritage of the tribe.
- **Intellectual or Material Cultural Heritage:** This includes the scientific legacies left by the elders and notable figures of the tribe,

such as arts, their interrelations, the practice of language, and its preservation within the activities of the Hamar tribe.

- **Material Cultural Heritage:** This encompasses everything produced by individuals within their tribe, all human-made tangible items such as clothing made from goat skins, furniture, and sculptures, within the activities of the Hamar tribe. It also includes everything acquired through the use and practice of their arts to the best extent.

Figure 5. represents one of the customs followed in preparing sculptures, jars, and tanning hides for making clothes.

3.4 The relationship with art and religious belief:

Research into the essence of art intertwines with the exploration of its purpose. As much as it reflects the image of society, it also attempts to transform it. The subject of art is "the beautiful," created through human work or action. Therefore, the variations in definitions provided to determine the nature of art stem from the differences in the environments and eras that fostered this art, as well as the perspectives of the researchers or scholars in the field of art.

Religion, on the other hand, has played a significant role in the development of civilizations and in solidifying beliefs and practices that regulate human behavior toward the sacred realm. It provides a comprehensive vision of the universe and the position of humans within it. Religion represents the sacred form encompassing everything related to the divine, as opposed to the profane, depicted in the film "Ethiopia on Foot: The Hamar Tribes."

However, the separation between art and religion in this society does not imply, as Van de Leeuw states, that the religious or sacred element has been completely and permanently excluded from all modern arts. On the contrary, we can find instances where religion relies on art in various contexts and through numerous examples, as it is deemed the most capable of conveying the sacred. Nevertheless, this separation was preceded by a bitter insistence by religion, or rather the interpretation of religion and religious consciousness, driven by political motives. It is noteworthy that this often appears during periods of cultural decline and regression. This occurred in a similar situation as described by Gadamer when the Roman Empire imposed restrictions and suppressed the freedom of rhetoric and poetic expression in the late period, which was lamented by Tacitus in his famous dialogue "Dialogue on Oratory (Tawfiq, 2017, p. 49)."

This is referred to as the alienation of aesthetic consciousness. Regardless of the different subjects of religion and art, this concept also expresses an intimate connection between them, intertwined within human consciousness. Throughout history, humans have attempted to express themselves through intentional activities not solely driven by instinct but accompanied by mixed and interwoven feelings of awe, wonder, and reverence. We witness this in ancient architecture and in the Christian and Islamic medieval periods. The varied forms of mosques, for example, express Muslims' consciousness of God's oneness, embodied in minarets, arabesques, geometric shapes, and Christian medieval paintings that often depict a spiritual Christian essence manifested in a state of tranquility and peace, as seen in the faces and gestures of the Holy Family and the saints.

3.5 The relationship through art, Language, And local heritage

The image of art in the realm of language becomes clear through the film under study and in all language sciences and arts. Dr. Haroun Al-Rababah emphasizes that the grammatical structure of a sentence is an art, the creation of Arabic terms is an art, and the importance of theatrical arts, stories, and novels in forming any dramatic work influences the language and contributes to shaping certain linguistic terms, such as the artistic imagery in poetry, the art of poetic meter, Arabic calligraphy, storytelling, and theater arts, among other language fields.

Based on this, the nature of ethnic diversity in Ethiopia is the complementary link and the other face of volumetric variation. For instance, the Amhara ethnicity, which surpasses the Afar ethnicity from the northeast, the Tigray from the north, and the Oromo from the south, intertwines and coheres with these three ethnicities to varying degrees. The language factor, which is one of the important cultural determinants of interaction and integration, differs among the four ethnicities. The Hamar tribe, for example, has its unique language, while Amharic is prevalent due to the cultural framework in Ethiopia.

In some of his previous studies, the researcher points out the use of architectural metaphors in art. Various studies and theses from global and international literature have addressed the use of language and art in the architectural field. For example, Aino Niskanen's study focuses on the importance of building materials in expressing inspiration from language and heritage and regional expression. Marwa Munzer Samin's study emphasizes literary and architectural translation for understanding and deconstruction, avoiding imitation and reproduction. Atta Hassan's study discusses integrating the heritage significance of postmodern architecture and linking form and meaning to achieve inclusion. Hassan Fathy's research highlights the use of traditional vocabulary with conventional building methods. Additionally, Imad Younes Lafi's valuable research explores finding scientific and aesthetic harmony between language and architecture (Fadel & Rzouqi).

Art has contributed to reviving heritage, bringing it out from the obscurity of forgetfulness to the shelves of libraries for researchers to discover. This has raised significant questions about customs and traditions, which are considered the most prominent elements of folk heritage linked to the daily practices of humans. The debate revolves around the possibility of preserving and enriching them since they reflect the experiences of ancestors and the identity of the community.

It is essential not to abandon them and to focus on the present through them, based on our current reality. Customs and traditions serve as the distinguishing card between different contemporary societies, where cultural, linguistic, and dialectical boundaries exist. In one country, there might be multiple communities differentiated by a set of practices, rituals, myths, customs, and traditions. Therefore, it is a significant mistake to

believe that folk or social customs can only be found in ancient inherited traditions. It is futile to limit their interpretation to their old forms and ancient origins. Folk customs are both a historical and contemporary phenomenon at the same time (Al-Johari, 2006, p. 38).

Men of the Hamar tribe work in livestock herding and agriculture, while women work in the corn and pea fields while taking care of their children. Their tasks also include cooking and fetching water due to the difficult social conditions the tribe faces. The tribe adheres to a daily ritual known as "bull jumping." A person carrying many sticks arrives, and girls gather around him. Each girl is given a stick, which she then hands to a young man she highly esteems, provided the young man is about to get married. This ritual indicates that the girl has reached both intellectual and physical maturity. The young man then strikes her on the lower back with the stick, and the harder the strike and the more it draws blood, the stronger the sign of love. Although it may cause bleeding, it is an accepted custom among them.

One of the practiced rituals involves women being struck on their backs, which is intended for maturation and preparation.

Figure

Among the inherited rituals of the Hamar tribe are those related to blessings. These blessings are ceremonial acts performed by the tribal elder as a sign of gratitude and appreciation for the presence and reception of guests (Ethiopia on Foot: The Hamar Tribes, n.d.). This is believed to bring rain and benefit the tribe's inhabitants. Additionally, the tribe practices a unique type of breakfast which involves drinking blood

mixed with milk as their daily morning meal (Ethiopia on Foot: The Hamar Tribes, n.d.), accompanied by their morning coffee, which they call "buna coffee."

3.6 Clothing and the art of dancing to chants and drums

As a form of material cultural heritage that constitutes a fundamental component of the cultural identity of tribes and peoples around the world, art receives it as a product that conveys their civilizational history. It represents a folk and cultural heritage in the Hamar tribe that can be invested in to expand and become a driver for social human practice and sustainable cultural development. Traditional clothing in this tribe, which includes some of the finest patterns in Ethiopia, is an integral part of the community and religious celebrations. Most tribe members use these traditional leather clothes, made from goat skin, for various festivities.

It is evident that most tribe members wear clothes made from animal skins as it provides a sense of inherited religious rituals passed down through generations, and it serves as official attire in various tribal events. Women of the tribe do not wear trousers; they usually wear only African attire. The dancers' costumes are designed to allow them freedom and ease of movement. The dancers' clothing consists of headbands that stiffen on the chest, adorned with embroidery and pearls, and other goat skin bands wrapped around the waist, from which thin fur folds hang. Additionally, they wear ankle bracelets with attached bells and small jingles, and a beaded collar. This attire, in general, leaves the shoulders bare.

The use of colorful and eye-catching fabric patterns is common, with both headties and long skirts often made from the same fabric. They often have a piece of cloth around their waist, which can be used for various purposes in different occasions.

Figure 7. Illustrates the method of using goat skin to make traditional clothing in the Hamer tribe.

What distinguishes the Hamer tribe in Ethiopia are the dances that blend together among the men, creating a tightly woven fabric of African life with its unique customs and traditions. These dances are accompanied by unique rituals of drumming and blowing horns, with dancers shouting and making strange movements and vibrations. Each dance is unique with its accompanying cries and sounds, especially during wedding ceremonies as per the tribe's traditions.

Figure 8. Illustrates how local dances are performed during the Afangadi night dance, which takes place approximately every month.

African dance circles are held at night after a day of work, with everyone participating. The Afangadi dance, a night dance held about every month, is closely connected to their lives and environments. It is not merely an abstract display of pure aesthetic values disconnected from reality. This

connection gives African dance its distinctive features in terms of form. Each African dance has a specific type of clothing and organized movement patterns, with vibrant-colored costumes typically made from goat skin.

As we observe through the documentary film, dancing in African societies is not considered a form of excitement, entertainment, and pleasure as it is commonly perceived in modern societies. Instead, it is a fundamental part of religious and social rituals. This is emphasized by Koffi Kôkô, one of the prominent figures in contemporary dance worldwide and a pioneer of modern African dance, who states: "Dance is wonderful because it conveys states and meanings without verbal language, allowing any spectator to interpret the dance in their own way, which is beyond our responsibility. It also gives the dancer freedom and the opportunity to own their language." Therefore, African dance is a truthful reflection of the conditions in which humans live in their environment.

Africans create music from everything; they can make all things resonate with melody. Their vast world is filled with thousands of sounds. They make their music from all aspects of their surroundings. In the Hamar tribe, music consists of the sounds of ankle bracelets and other musical instruments accompanying the bull-jumping ritual. This serves as the primary linguistic text guiding the dance performance before the audience and is used as a prominent means of social communication among them. To this day, history has not recorded a civilization excelling in the arts of dance like that of the African continent, showcasing their immense ability to embody human emotion (Ethiopia on Foot: The Hamar Tribes, n.d.).

3.7 The art of camouflage and decoration

To shed light on the principles of analyzing the artistic and social practices of the Hamar tribe, we must delve into the concept of the mask. The word mask can mean "black" or "witch," both meanings stemming from religious rituals. In the Dionysian rites related to Dionysus, worshippers would smear their faces with wine dregs and vine leaves. From this sacrificial celebration, the use of masks specifically crafted for this purpose evolved. Thus, the initial concept of the mask was linked to

religious rituals and ceremonies. It was part of these primitive religious rites aimed, through magic, at confronting nature.

The mask among Hamar men is manifested through the wrinkles on the faces of tribe members due to the harsh conditions they live in. However, the mask's features become evident through the makeup practiced by the men of the tribe. This makeup distinguishes itself from that of other individuals, especially for the ritual of striking girls during the bull-jumping ceremony, with faces painted in various bright and clear colors.

Figure 9. Depicts the significant facial paintings used by young men in preparation for the bull-jumping ritual. This painting or mask distinguishes each man from the others.

Conclusions

African art reflects the inner life of African communities and serves as a mirror of life connected to nature. It is a tool for preserving identity, customs, and values, and an instrument of education and enlightenment. The African man has often used artistic practices as a social bond, an intellectual weapon, and a means of cultural, political, and religious awareness, as well as a way to maintain identity and, at times, as a form of therapy. Thus, the documentary film serves various functions, including religious, social, therapeutic, educational, and entertaining roles. Ethnography here is not merely a phenomenon but an expression of human life, and humanity cannot be understood or imagined outside the context of society.

It is noteworthy that in these religious rituals, the mask embodies the worshipped deity, becoming the god/mask. Furthermore, the mask began to be used in Greek, Roman, and Indian plays, where the actor would wear it during the performance to astonish or frighten, change appearances or facial expressions, or transform the character to conceal emotions or as a means of illusion. The mask transcended its theatrical concept to merge with the character, unify with it, or adhere to the voice of the character wearing the mask.

One of the characteristics of the African man is his strong connection to his community, as highlighted by the documentary film, which raises audience awareness and guides them towards noble principles, values, and ethics to reinforce their belonging to their ethnic group or tribe, and pride in their history and heroic past. The following results were reached:

- The documentary film aims to gather as many ethnographic documents as possible to help uncover the truth.
- African art allows for the depiction of reality with artistic touches that attract the viewer.
- The African man delves deeply into social realities, phenomena, and issues, examining the impacts of customs and traditions in Africa.

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